

SQLITE MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASIGA ULANISH VA FAYL YARATISH HAQIDA TAFSILOTI MALUMOT BERISH

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Anotatsiya: SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasi fayl asosidagi ma'lumotlar bazasidir, ya'ni barcha ma'lumotlar bitta faylda saqlanadi. SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan ishlash uchun Python dasturlash tilidan foydalaniladi. Pythonning sqlite3 kutubxonasi SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasiga ulanish va SQL so'rovlarini bajarish imkonini beradi. Bu tezisdagi SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasida jadval yaratish, jadvalga ma'lumot qo'shish, jadvaldan ma'lumot olish, jadvalni o'zgartirish yoki o'chirish kabi amallar namunaviy kodlar orqali namoyish etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: SQL, Python, table, cursor

Аннотация: База данных SQLite представляет собой базу данных на основе файлов, что означает, что все данные хранятся в одном файле. Для работы с базой данных SQLite используется язык программирования Python. Библиотека Python sqlite3 позволяет подключаться к базам данных SQLite и выполнять запросы SQL. В этой диссертации такие действия, как создание таблицы в базе данных SQLite, добавление информации в таблицу, получение информации из таблицы, изменение или удаление таблицы, демонстрируются с помощью примеров кода.

Ключевые слова: SQL, Python, таблица, курсор.

Abstract: A SQLite database is a file-based database, which means that all data is stored in a single file. The Python programming language is used to work with the SQLite database. Python's sqlite3 library allows you to connect to SQLite databases and execute SQL queries. In this thesis, actions such as creating a table in the SQLite database, adding information to the table, getting information from the table, changing or deleting the table are demonstrated through sample codes.

Keywords: SQL, Python, table, cursor

Ma'lumotlar bazasi dasturlash sohasida SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasi keng tarqalgan va oson ishlatiladigan vositalardan biridir. SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasi fayl asosidagi ma'lumotlar bazasidir, ya'ni barcha ma'lumotlar bitta faylda saqlanadi. Bu esa SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasini portativ va engil qiladi. SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasi SQL (Structured Query Language) so'rovlarini bajarish uchun dasturlash tilini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Bu maqolada biz Python dasturlash tilidan foydalanib, SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasiga qanday ulanish va fayl yaratishni ko'rib chiqamiz.

SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasiga ulanish va fayl yaratish uchun quyidagi bosqichlarni amalga oshiramiz:

sqlite3 kutubxonasini import qilish. sqlite3 kutubxonasi Pythonning standart kutubxonalari orasida bo'lib, alohida o'rnatish talab qilmaydi. Bu kutubxona SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasiga ulanish va SQL so'rovlarini bajarish imkonini beradi.

sqlite3.connect() funksiyasini chaqirish. Bu funksiya ma'lumotlar bazasi faylining yo'lini argument sifatida qabul qiladi. Agar fayl mavjud bo'lmasa, sqlite3 moduli bo'sh ma'lumotlar

bazasi yaratadi. Bu funksiya ulanish obyektini qaytaradi, bu obyekt orqali biz SQL so'rovlarini yuborishimiz mumkin.

cursor() metodini chaqirish. Ulanish obyektidan cursor() metodini chaqirib, kursor obyektini olishimiz kerak. Kursor obyektining vazifasi SQL so'rovlarini bajarish va natijalarni olishdir².

execute() metodini chaqirish. Kursor obyektidan execute() metodini chaqirib, SQL so'rovlarini yuborishimiz kerak. Bu metod SQL so'rovining satrini argument sifatida qabul qiladi. Biz CREATE TABLE so'rovi yordamida yangi jadval yaratishimiz mumkin.

commit() metodini chaqirish. Ulanish obyektidan commit() metodini chaqirib, o'zgarishlarni saqlashimiz kerak². Agar biz commit() metodini chaqirmasak, o'zgarishlar yo'qolishi mumkin.

close() metodini chaqirish. Ulanish obyektidan close() metodini chaqirib, ulanishni yopishimiz kerak. Bu amalni bajarishdan oldin commit() metodini chaqirganligimizga ishonch hosil qiling.

Quyidagi kodda biz Python dasturlash tili yordamida SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasiga ulanib, yangi fayl va jadval yaratamiz:

```
# sqlite3 kutubxonasini import qilamiz
import sqlite3
# SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasiga ulanamiz va yangi fayl yaratamiz
conn = sqlite3.connect("test.db")
# Kursor obyektini olamiz
cur = conn.cursor()
# Yangi jadval yaratamiz
cur.execute("CREATE TABLE person (name TEXT, age INTEGER)")
# O'zgarishlarni saqlaymiz
conn.commit()
# Ulanishni yopamiz
conn.close()
```

Bu kodni ishga tushirsak, test.db deb nomlangan yangi fayl yaratiladi va uning ichida person deb nomlangan jadval mavjud bo'ladi.

Xulosa

Bu tezisdan biz Python dasturlash tilidan foydalanib, SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasiga qanday ulanish va fayl yaratishni ko'rib chiqdik. Biz sqlite3 kutubxonasining asosiy funksiyalaridan va metodlaridan foydalandik. SQLite ma'lumotlar bazasi bilan ishlashning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari haqida ham gaplashdik.

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